

The Subspecies of Life: 34 Names at New Rank in *Copiapoa*, *Cylindropuntia*, *Echinocereus*, *Eriosyce*, *Mammillaria*, *Opuntia*, *Turbiniacarpus* and *Trichocereus* (Cactaceae)

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Abstract—34 names at subspecific rank are proposed for cactus taxa currently accepted at the rank of variety.

Following the recommendation by the IOS Working Party to use the rank of subspecies instead of that of variety (Hunt, *New Cactus Lexicon*: 4. 2006), the following taxa, all currently accepted at the rank of variety in *Plants of the World Online* (<https://powo.science.kew.org/>, accessed March 2, 2022), are hereby reclassified as subspecies.

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Copiapoa

Copiapoa coquimbana subsp. *wagenknechtii* (F.Ritter) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Copiapoa coquimbana* var. *wagenknechtii* F.Ritter, Taxon 12: 30 (1963).

Copiapoa echinoides subsp. *cuprea* (F.Ritter) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Copiapoa cuprea* F.Ritter, Cactus, Paris xiv. No. 63: 136 (1959).

Cylindropuntia

Cylindropuntia fulgida subsp. *mamillata* (A.Schott ex Engelm.) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Opuntia mamillata* A.Schott ex Engelm., Proc. Amer. Acad. Arts 3: 308 (1856).

Echinocereus

Echinocereus engelmannii subsp. *acicularis* (L.D.Benson) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Echinocereus engelmannii* var. *acicularis* L.D.Benson, Cacti Ariz. ed. 3: 22 (1969).

Echinocereus engelmannii subsp. *xiphizon* (L.D.Benson) M.H.J.van der Meer **nom. et stat. nov.** ≡ *Echinocereus engelmannii* var. *armatus* L.D.Benson, Cact. Succ. J. (Los Angeles) 41: 33 (1969). A new epithet is proposed to avoid confusion with *Echinocereus reichenbachii* subsp. *armatus* (Poselg.) N.P.Taylor. Etymology: Greek *xiphizon* 'dancing the sword dance'. For the formidable spination.

Echinocereus engelmannii subsp. *chrysocentrus* (Engelm. & J.M.Bigelow) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Cereus engelmannii* var. *chrysocentrus* Engelm. & J.M.Bigelow, Proc. Amer. Acad. Arts 3: 283 (1856).

Echinocereus engelmannii subsp. *howei* (L.D.Benson) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Echinocereus engelmannii* var. *howei* L.D.Benson, Cact. Succ. J. (Los Angeles) 46: 80 (1974).

Echinocereus engelmannii subsp. *munzii* (Parish) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Cereus munzii* Parish, Bull. S. Calif. Acad. Sci. 25: 48 (1926).

Echinocereus engelmannii subsp. *porphyrogenitus* M.H.J.van der Meer **nom. et stat. nov.** ≡ *Echinocereus engelmannii* var. *purpureus* L.D.Benson, Cact. Succ. J. (Los Angeles) 41: 126 (1969). A new epithet is proposed to avoid confusion with *Echinocereus purpureus* Lahman (= *Echinocereus reichenbachii* (Terscheck) Haage subsp. *reichenbachii*). Etymology: Latin *porphyrogenitus* (Greek *porphyrogennetos*) 'purple-born'. For the central spines, which are bright purple when young.

Echinocereus enneacanthus subsp. *carnosus* (Rümppler) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Echinocereus carnosus* Rümppler, Handb. Cacteenk. (ed. 2 - Rümppler) ed. 2: 796 (1886).

Echinocereus viridiflorus subsp. *neocapillus* (D.Weniger) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Echinocereus chloranthus* var. *neocapillus* D.Weniger, Cact. Succ. J. (Los Angeles) 41: 39, fig. 4 (1969).

Eriosyce

Eriosyce aurata subsp. *spinibarbis* (F.Ritter) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Eriosyce spinibarbis* F.Ritter, Kakteen Südamerika 3: 915 (1980).

Eriosyce chilensis subsp. *albidiflora* (F.Ritter) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Pyrrhocactus chilensis* var. *albidiflorus* F.Ritter, Kakteen Südamerika 3: 927 (1980).

Eriosyce curvispina* subsp. *aconcaguensis (F.Ritter) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Pyrrhocactus aconcaguensis* F.Ritter, Succulenta (Netherlands) 1960: 108 (1960).

Eriosyce curvispina* subsp. *choapensis (F.Ritter) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Pyrrhocactus choapensis* F.Ritter, Succulenta (Netherlands) 1960: 133 (1960).

Eriosyce curvispina* subsp. *mutabilis (F.Ritter) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Pyrrhocactus horridus* var. *mutabilis* F.Ritter, Kakteen Südamerika 3: 946 (1980).

Eriosyce curvispina* subsp. *robusta (F.Ritter) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Pyrrhocactus robustus* F.Ritter, Succulenta (Netherlands) 1960: 65 (1960).

Eriosyce marksiana* subsp. *lissocarpa (F.Ritter) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Pyrrhocactus lissocarpus* F.Ritter, Succulenta (Netherlands) 1960: 17 (1960).

Mammillaria

Mammillaria blossfeldiana* subsp. *shurlyana (H.E.Gates) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Mammillaria shurlyana* ('*shurliana*') H.E.Gates, Cact. Succ. J. Gr. Brit. 18: 30 (1956). Etymology: Named for Ernest William Shurly. The spelling *shurliana* is correctable to *shurlyana* under article 60.9 of the International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Shenzhen Code): 'When changes in spelling by authors who adopt personal [...] names in nomenclature are intentional latinizations, they are to be preserved, except, in epithets formed from personal names, when they concern [...] personal names in which the changes involve only [...] conversion of the terminal vowel to a different vowel, for which the omitted or converted letter is to be restored.' ([Turland & al. in Regnum Veg. 159. 2018](#)).

Opuntia

Opuntia elata subsp. *delaetiana* (F.A.C.Weber) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Opuntia elata* var. *delaetiana* F.A.C.Weber, Bull. Mus. Hist. Nat. (Paris) 10: 392 (1904).

Opuntia elata subsp. *rioplatensis* (Font) M.H.J.van der Meer **comb. et stat. nov.** ≡ *Opuntia elata* var. *obovata* E.Walther, J. Cact. Succ. Soc. Amer. 1: 204, figs. 2, 4 (1930) ≡ *Opuntia rioplatensis* ('*rioplatense*') Font, Succ. Pl. Res. 8: 85 (2014).

Opuntia engelmannii subsp. *cuija* (Griffiths & Hare) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Opuntia engelmannii* var. *cuija* Griffiths & Hare, New Mexico Agric. Exp. Sta. Bull. 60: 44, t. 2 (1906).

Opuntia engelmannii subsp. *laevis* (J.M.Coult.) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Opuntia laevis* J.M.Coult., Contr. U.S. Natl. Herb. 3(7): 419 (1896).

Opuntia galapageia subsp. *gigantea* (J.T.Howell) M.H.J.van der Meer **comb. in stat. nov.** ≡ *Opuntia echios* subsp. *gigantea* J.T.Howell, Proc. Calif. Acad. Sci. ser. 4, 21: 51, tab. 3, fig. 4 (1933).

Opuntia galapageia subsp. *helleri* (K.Schum. ex B.L.Rob.) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Opuntia helleri* K.Schum., Proc. Amer. Acad. Arts 38(4): 180 (1902).

Opuntia galapageia subsp. *macrocarpa* (E.Y.Dawson) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Opuntia galapageia* var. *macrocarpa* E.Y.Dawson, Cact. Succ. J. (Los Angeles) 37: 141 (1965).

Opuntia galapageia subsp. *profusa* (E.F.Anderson & Walk.) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Opuntia galapageia* var. *profusa* E.F.Anderson & Walk., Madroño 20: 256 (1970).

Opuntia galapageia subsp. *saxicola* (J.T.Howell) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Opuntia saxicola* J.T.Howell, Proc. Calif. Acad. Sci. ser. 4, 21: 45, tab. 2, fig. 1 (1933).

Opuntia littoralis subsp. *piercei* (Fosberg) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Opuntia phaeacantha* var. *piercei* Fosberg, Bull. S. Calif. Acad. Sci. 33: 102 (1934).

Opuntia megapotamica subsp. *chadihuensis* (Oakley & Villamil) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Opuntia megapotamica* var. *chadihuensis* Oakley & Villamil, Botany (Ottawa) 95: 115 (2017).

Opuntia polyacantha subsp. *nicholii* (L.D.Benson) M.H.J.van der Meer **stat. nov.** ≡ *Opuntia nicholii* L.D.Benson, Cacti Ariz. ed. 2: 48 (1950).

Turbinicarpus

Turbinicarpus schmiedickeanus subsp. *kupcakii* (Halda & Horáček) M.H.J.van der Meer **comb. in stat. nov.** ≡ *Turbinicarpus macrochele* subsp. *kupcakii* Halda & Horáček, Acta Mus. Richnov., Sect. Nat. 7(2): 76 (2000).

Trichocereus

Trichocereus macrogonus subsp. *sanpedro* M.H.J.van der Meer **nom. et stat. nov.**
≡ *Trichocereus padanoi* Britton & Rose, Cactaceae (Britton & Rose) 2: 134(-135; fig. 196) (1920). The change of rank allows the adoption of an epithet based on the widely known indigenous name 'cactus de San Pedro' (cf. [Gillman & Wright, Commun. Biol. 3: 609. 2020](#); [Knapp, Vorontsova & Turland, Taxon 69\(6\): 1409-1410. 2020](#)).

